

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example; 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. But There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the IRRN should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in IRRN contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Agronomic characteristics

Local indica rice varieties with desirable floral traits influencing outcrossing

H. C. Sarkar, plant breeder, and N. M. Miah, principal plant breeder, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

We sought to identify local indica rice varieties with desirable floral traits influencing outcrossing at BRRI main station, Joydebpur, during the 1982 transplanted aman season (Jul-Dec). Ninety-eight local varieties were grown in 5.4- × 2-m plots at 25- × 15-cm spacing using one seedling/hill. No fertilizer was applied.

Anther size (length), stigma size (length), and stigma exertion (%) were recorded for each entry. Anther length varied from 0.97 to 2.80 mm ($\bar{X} = 2.08 \pm 0.03$); stigma length from 0.42 to 1.34 mm ($\bar{X} = 0.85 \pm 0.02$); and stigma exser-

Varieties with larger anthers (≥ 2.00 mm long) and stigmata (≥ 1.00 mm long) with good exsertion ($\geq 50\%$).

Variety	Anther length (mm)	Stigma length (mm)	Stigma exertion (%)
Ashwini	2.04	1.04	50
Kalagura	2.28	1.00	70
Lal Khama	2.08	1.04	60
Kumri	2.10	1.04	60
Loatung	2.10	1.06	75
Dhalai ropa	2.30	1.00	75
Holud jaron	2.14	1.00	70
Rajbhog	2.10	1.34	70
Kanpasha	2.18	1.14	80
Laida	2.48	1.08	75

tion from 0 to 90% ($\bar{X} = 46.24 \pm 2.58$).

Ten entries had larger anthers (≥ 2.00 mm) and stigmata (≥ 1.00 mm) with good exertion ($\geq 50\%$) (see table). The distribution of varieties by anther length, stigma length, and stigma exertion is shown in the figure. □

Varieties (no.)

Frequency distribution of varieties by anther length, stigma length, and stigma exertion.

Rice seed viability under two storage conditions

Md. Zahurul Haque and Mahmuda Haroon, Plant Physiology Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

BR8 and BR9, two high yielding varieties (HYVs) recently released by BRRI for boro and aus seasons, yield better than

other HYVs, but field workers reported that germination percentage, particularly that of BR9, was poor. Rapid loss of seed viability was suspected to be a genetic trait.

We studied the seed viability range of BR8 and BR9, with BR3 as check. Boro-harvested seeds were sun-dried to 12% moisture (wet basis) and stored in metal baby food containers and in gunny bags

in a laboratory room, Seed viability was checked at monthly intervals by germinating the seeds in water culture at 32°C in the germinator. using 100 seeds and 3 replications.

Seed viability remained high until 352 days from harvest when seeds were stored in metal containers. BR9 germination percentage was highest (see figure). BR8 and BR9 seeds stored in gunny bags lost viability much more rapidly than BR3. A similar trend in seed viability loss was recorded in aus-harvested BR3, BR8, and BR9 seed, except that viability range was shorter for boro-harvested seeds.

It appears that BR8 and BR9 seeds are more susceptible to exposure to the atmosphere (gunny bag storage) although their genetic potential for seed viability range is higher than that of BR3, as indicated by storage in a closed metal container. It is suggested that the seeds of these varieties be carefully stored and handled to minimize exposure to high humidity associated with high temperatures. □

Germination percentage of boro-harvested rice seeds stored in closed metal containers (a) and in gunny bags (b), and mean temperature and mean relative humidity (RH) of storeroom.

Inheritance of leaf sheath color in rice

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We studied the inheritance of purple leaf-sheath coloration using the parents Tai-

chung Native 1 (TN1) with a green leaf sheath, and Dular with a purple leaf sheath, F₁ and F₂ populations of the cross TN1/Dular, and backcrosses of F₁/TN1 and F₁/Dular.

The distributions of parents, F₁, F₂, and backcross progenies are shown in

Table 1. Color varied from deep purple to green. Plants were grouped as colored (purple) and green as shown in Table 2.

The purple leaf sheath was dominant in F₁ and the difference between the two was monogenic. F₂ data also indicated that the purple leaf sheath is dominant and is conditioned by a single gene. The backcross plants of F₁/TN1 confirmed the finding, indicating that a pair of alleles condition segregation in crosses between parents with purple leaf sheaths (Tables 1 and 2). □

Table 1. Distribution of parents, F₁, F₂, and backcross progenies.

Parent or progeny	Plants (no.) in each class					Total plants (no.)
	Purple	Intermediate	dark purple	Light purple	Green	
TN1					60	60
Dular	58					58
F ₁	3		19			22
F ₂	22		128	98	99	347
BC(F ₁ /TN1)	5		27		23	55
BC(F ₁ /Dular)	15		5			20

Table 2. Segregation in F₂ progeny of TN1/Dular, backcross progeny of F₁/TN1 and F₁/Dular for leaf sheath color.

Cross	Plants (no.)			Expected ratio	X ²	P value
	Colored ^a	Green	Total			
TN1/Dular	248	99	347	3:1	2.12	0.20-0.10
F ₁ /TN1	32	23	55	1:1	1.16	0.30-0.20
F ₁ /Dular	20	0	20	No seg.		

^a Colored represents all classes of purple, purple intermediate, dark purple, and light purple.

ERRATUM

T. N. Singh, Gulab Singh, and H. P. Singh. Chemical weed control in dryland rice. IRRN 7 (5) (Oct 1982), 21-22. In the table on page 22, the last row should read:

CD (5%) 0.17 0.20